

The contribution of practicing the physical and the recreational sport activity in improving the quality of life levels for medical practitioners corps

Abdelaaziz khalfi*¹, mostapha boudebza.²

¹Khemis Miliana University, abdelaaziz.khalfi@univ-dbk.m.dz

Laboratory of Sport, Health and Performance

² Khemis Miliana University , m.boudebza@univ-dbk.m.dz

Laboratory of Sport, Health and Performance

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Abstract: The goal of the study was to ascertain how engaging in recreational and physical sports activities could enhance the quality of life for the corps of medical practitioners. The descriptive survey method was used by the researchers .The quality of life scale, developed by the World Health Organization and translated into Arabic by physician Bouchra Ismail Ahmed (2008), was utilized in order to meet the study's objectives. The study came to differing conclusions. Among them is the benefit of engaging in recreational and physical sports activities for enhancing one's quality of life.

Keywords : Quality of life -Recreational sport activity-Medical corp.

المخلص: هدفت الدراسة إلى الكشف عن اسهامات ممارسة النشاط البدني الرياضي الترويحي في تحسين مستوى أبعاد جودة الحياة لدى افراد السلك الطبي الممارسين ، وقد اتبع الباحثان المنهج الوصفي المسحي، ولتحقيق أهداف الدراسة قاما باستخدام مقياس جودة الحياة الذي أعدته منظمة الصحة العالمية، وقامت بتعريبه الدكتورة بشرى اسماعيل أحمد (2008) . وقد توصلت الدراسة إلى عدة نتائج أهمها الدور الايجابي لممارسة النشاط البدني الرياضي الترويحي في تحسين أبعاد جودة الحياة.

الكلمات المفتاحية: جودة الحياة ، النشاط الرياضي الترويحي ، السلك الطبي.

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1.Introduction:

In the present time, quality of life is a global trend at the level of institutions or sectors. All of them talk about quality of life, as it helps to improve and raise collective and individual productivity. This term has become one of the modern concepts, which is considered one of the basic variables of the personality, and a fundamental goal in the life of the individual that creative people from philosophers, experts, and thinkers strive to achieve. Achieving it leads to a feeling of satisfaction, enjoyment, joy, self-realization, optimism, and thus a positive attitude towards life. The importance of this topic is due to the nature of life, personal and social adaptation, and the investment of positive aspects. This term is also used to assess the general well-being of individuals and societies. It is also used in a wide range of contexts, including international development, healthcare, and political science. The concept of quality of life should not be confused with the concept of standard of living, which is based primarily on income. Instead, quality of life measurement indicators do not only include wealth and job opportunities, but also urban environment, physical and mental health, education, entertainment, leisure time, and social belonging. It also includes the quality of life that a person lives or represents in the reality that the person lives in himself.

Human resources are one of the basic resources in different institutions. The effectiveness of all the institution's resources depends on the efficiency of human resources in managing it. Through the human element, the real benefit of other resources is realized, such as raw materials, capital, management, marketing, and others. Moreover, human resources, with their ability to renew, innovate, innovate, and develop, can overcome the scarcity of other resources. (Al-Shanti , 2018, p. 15)

The health sector is a cornerstone of the public service in our country. Its significance stems from the crucial tasks it undertakes and the multitude of activities it carries out, all aimed at safeguarding and promoting the health of Algerian citizens. These activities encompass a wide range of human, cultural, scientific, and economic dimensions, solidifying the sector's central role in matters of public development. It embodies both the objective and the means of development simultaneously.

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While human resources might be considered secondary in some systems compared to material and technical resources, in the health sector, they take center stage. The unique nature of the healthcare system and its clientele revolves around this vital human element. The effective functioning of the healthcare system hinges entirely on its human resources, further diversified into various professional categories with distinct job profiles, requirements, and professional and personal aspirations.

Nursing and medicine are also two vital professions in our societies, where they form the vast majority of healthcare workers . (Abbas, 2009, p. 123) Medical personnel are one of the most important human elements in society, as they provide humanitarian and healing services, such as treating individuals, providing assistance, performing surgical interventions, etc. This is a demanding task that requires providing a set of material, psychological, and physical factors.

This is where the interest of major organizations in employee quality of life comes from, as it is considered the most important resource for the organization. Laws and regulations began to be enacted at the beginning of the last century to protect workers from work-related injuries. In the early 1930s, the activities of labor unions and associations began to focus on the occupational security of workers. This led to the 1950s and 1960s, when academic researchers began to develop in-depth theories on the subject of work quality of life by working to find a positive relationship between production on the one hand, and the morale of workers and human relations on the other. (Al-Shanti , 2018, p. 16)

A recent study by the World Health Organization (WHO) found that insufficient physical activity has a negative impact on mental health and quality of life in general. This is considered a major risk factor for non-communicable diseases.

Leisure is a social phenomenon that pervades human societies, at different cultural levels and in multiple and diverse forms, determined by the cultural, social, and economic context. The importance of engaging in leisure activities in filling free time is evident, as the progress and development of countries is measured by how their members invest their free time. (Abd el Hamid & Ahmed Rabie , 1998, p. 01) Leisure activities are one of the solutions that provide different social strata, at different cultural levels, with the opportunity

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to find social and psychological balance. The effects associated with these sports skills in team play aim to develop the individual through the joint effort of each player. The nature of competition also provides men and women with the opportunity to participate at an advanced age, maintaining the necessary fitness to enable them to bear the burdens of life and enjoy health and happiness through the practice of various activities such as athletics and positive games that have the characteristic of participation.

In this way, recreation is in accordance with human nature and achieves balance in the human soul and drives to happiness. It is well known that the human soul naturally tends to what brings it happiness. Therefore, leisure activity is a protection for the individual, in which the individual expresses his feelings, develops his mind, understands, produces, increases his knowledge and information, his energy is released, he innovates, his directions are adjusted, and his inclinations grow, so life acquires its luster and becomes more joyful and radiant. It achieves satisfaction for the individual, a sense of belonging, and organization of his time and improvement of his physical and mental health.

Many studies have shown that regular exercise helps to reduce work-related stress and contributes to achieving and improving the quality of life of its practitioners. It helps to achieve happiness for humans, as it works to develop physical and mental health, as well as to promote emotionality and morality. It also contributes to raising morale and a sense of security. In addition, there are scientific studies that have shown that a physically fit person can accomplish their tasks with less effort and more efficiency, and continue to work with the same effectiveness for a long time without feeling bored, tired, or stressed.

The feeling of quality of life as a result of practicing recreational sports by members of the medical staff is a relative matter because it is related to some subjective factors such as the positive concept of the self, satisfaction with life, work, and social status. It is also related to some objective factors such as available financial resources, income, environmental cleanliness, health and mental status, housing and employment status.

As an inevitable result of the strong evidence that indicates the close relationship between physical activity on the one hand and the mental and physical health of humans on the other hand, many

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recommendations and documents have been issued by organizations and bodies responsible for and concerned with human health, emphasizing physical activity and following a more active and active lifestyle. Among these documents, for example, is what was issued by the World Health Organization in 2004, which culminated in its interest in this topic and its international strategies for food and physical activity . (WHO, 2004)

Problem statement:

The health sector contributes to improving the quality of services provided to patients by providing the best medical and therapeutic services and the best possible means from doctors and nurses, and by taking care to reduce the problem of premature death and the slowness in providing treatment. For this reason, the professions of nursing and medicine are considered noble and humanitarian professions because of their association with human health and the preservation of life and the relief of suffering. The medical staff play a distinguished role in caring for the patient around the clock in various healthcare institutions, which requires effort in monitoring patients, providing them with health care, and paying attention to them, in addition to continuous stay and longer periods, and exposure to severe emergency cases and the night shift system that isolates them from the pace of social life and causes them sleep disturbances, in addition to feelings of frustration, anxiety, and anger from the reactions of the patient's relatives or companions. The profession of medicine and nursing is exposed to obstacles that prevent the employee from performing his role effectively and includes a great deal of hardship or stress due to the many situations in which the nurse finds himself unable to provide a helping hand to the patient or his relatives. Martin Paul (2001) pointed out that psychological stress can generate the desire for the individual to engage in compensatory behaviors, including smoking, addiction, eating large amounts of unhealthy foods, refraining from taking natural remedies, stopping beneficial exercises for the body, and taking steroids (Souriya & Ahman, 2018, p. 58) of these situations and the practice of unhealthy habits and behaviors by medical staff have a negative impact on their mental and physical health, making them susceptible to various diseases and reflecting negatively on their performance at work and their lives in general.

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Therefore, recreational sports activity has become a successful and purposeful therapeutic means more than just enjoying leisure time. It gives the individual in general and the employee in particular experiences that help to enjoy life. The effect of its practice is also evident in developing self-confidence and self-reliance on the sporting spirit in a way that takes the individual out of isolation and integrates him well into society. This encouraged us to conduct this research in order to identify the levels of quality of life among nurses and doctors. Where the segment of doctors and nurses represents a fundamental pillar in the health system and it represents the largest number of employees of the Ministry of Health, we see it as a duty to give it its right to research and study in order to identify and elevate that profession and its workers. And in our belief in the role that sport in general and recreational sports activity in particular plays in maintaining human health, we thought that we should delve into the study of this topic, trying to help this segment of society by highlighting the importance of practicing recreational physical sports activity in improving the dimensions of quality of life among medical personnel. And the problem of the study is highlighted in:

What is the extent of the contributions of practicing recreational sports activities to improving the dimensions of quality of life among doctors and nurses?.

Hypotheses:

Recreational physical activity contributes significantly to improving the quality of life dimensions of medical personnel.

Objectives of the study:

* This study aimed to know and explore the general level of quality of life among doctors and nurses working in hospitals who practice recreational physical activity.

* To reveal the variation and difference in their level of quality of life.

* To identify the differences in the level of quality of life dimensions between nurses and doctors.

Importance of the study:

The importance of this study lies in the following:

This study targets an important professional segment that has a great burden in providing health care to society in light of the special conditions in which the society lives, from diseases and injuries resulting from the lifestyle.

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Therefore, we wanted to shed light on this important segment of society that has not received much attention from researchers in the Arab world in general and in Algeria in particular. Also, to define the components of quality of life and to stand up to its improvement.

2. Theoretical Framework:

Research Terms:

Medical:

A group of people with integrated skills, shared objectives, a single purpose, and a common entry point for their work are referred to as the medical profession. This term is chosen because it encompasses health professionals who work as general or specialty physicians, perform their duties in public or private hospitals, and are motivated to complete a single, complex medical task. Because it does not represent a moral self, the medical treatment is not recognized by the law. (harehira & mahfoudh , 2022)

Quality of life:

it means the extent to which the individual feels satisfaction and happiness and his ability to satisfy his needs through the quality of the environment in which he lives and the services provided to him in the health, social, educational, and psychological fields, with good time management and exploitation. (Mansi & Kazim, 2010)

The Challenges of Defining Quality of Life:

* Defining quality of life is a challenging task for several reasons, including:

Experts in different scientific fields have each claimed that the study of this concept is their exclusive domain. As a result, there are many different and conflicting definitions of quality of life. Some have used it to measure the effectiveness of medical and social service programs, while others have used it to express notions of progress or to assess individuals' perceptions of their own well-being.

* The concept of quality of life is ambiguous because it is used in a variety of contexts and disciplines .It can refer to health, happiness, self-esteem, mental health, or life satisfaction. As a result, there is no single agreed-upon definition or way to measure quality of life.

* The concept of quality of life changes over time and with changes in an individual's psychological state and life stage.Happiness, for example, can have different meanings for the same individual in different contexts. A sick person may find happiness in health, while a

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poor person may find happiness in money. In this way, concepts of quality of life change with changes in the individual's circumstances (Al-Hindawi , 2011)

*The concept of quality of life is a relative concept that varies from person to person, both theoretically and practically, based on the criteria that individuals rely on to assess life and its requirements, which are often affected by many factors that control the determination of the components of quality of life, such as.

The ability to think, make decisions, and the ability to control and manage surrounding conditions Physical and mental health, Economic and social conditions, Religious beliefs, Cultural and civilizational values that individuals determine the important and most important things through, which achieve their happiness in life (Al-Hums, (2010, p. 45).

- The novelty of the concept at the level of accurate scientific treatment.

This concept is not associated with a specific field of life or a specific branch of science, but rather it is a concept distributed among researchers and scientists of different specializations. It is noteworthy that the owners of each specialization believe that they are the most entitled to use this concept, whether they are specialized in sociology, medicine with its different branches, environmental sciences, or economics. (Ramadan, 2012, p. 18)

However, we find that there are many aspects that have addressed the concept of quality of life, despite the difficulties mentioned above. There are four main trends in defining quality of life.

***The philosophical trend**

This trend confirms that the concept of quality of life is a right to equal life and prosperity. There are many indicators that indicate that a person enjoys quality of life, and one of them is happiness.

Psychological Approach:

Relied on individual perception as a fundamental determinant of the concept and the relationship between the concept and other psychological concepts, the most important of which are values, psychological needs and their satisfaction, self-realization, mental health, self-confidence, and levels of ambition in the individual.

Social Approach:

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Includes relationships , financial interests, and social support. The human being is social by nature and needs others for his happiness. Also, enjoying good health, high functional ability, high income, and social relationships with family, friends, and colleagues are among the most important factors that determine the quality of life (Al-Kharafi, 2013, p. 29)

Medical Approach:

The medical approach relied on identifying quality of life indicators, and did not define a definition of this concept. The interest of doctors, social specialists, and researchers in the social sciences has clearly increased in promoting and improving the quality of life of patients through providing them with psychological and social support. Medical specialists define quality of life as organic function, while psychiatrists view quality of life in conjunction with the interrelated relationships between the organic, emotional, and social spheres (Al-Ajami, 2015, pp. 19-20)

Despite all the controversy surrounding the establishment of a unified definition of quality of life, there is agreement among researchers on a set of characteristics that distinguish this concept, These characteristics are:

Multiplicity of factors and dimensions:

Between the physical condition, the psychological and emotional condition, the functional skills, the social condition, and the material and economic conditions. It is a state of physical, social, psychological, economic, emotional, and religious integration.

Non-stability:

Where the way of life does not express a stable state, or a specific situation at a specific time.

Non-normative:

Where there is no reference to adjust it. The individual himself is the party and determines it, and the individual concerned remains the only one capable of determining and adjusting it. So it is a decision and the individual is

responsible for achieving or improving it.

Recreational sports activities:

are those types of recreation that include many physical and sports programs. They are also the most influential types of recreation on the

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physical and physiological aspects of the individual who practices its aspects, which include games and sports (operational definition).

Purposes of Recreational Sports Activities:

The need for recreation leads the individual to search day after day for a life rich in meaning, joy, and happiness, a life characterized by balance between work and recreation. Therefore, the philosophy of recreation as one of the manifestations of daily life is a natural and spontaneous expression of some of the individual's interests and needs, which changes, but is adjusted by practice. The recreational purposes can be summarized according to recreational interests and desires that can be considered as motivations for practicing recreational activities during. It consists of:

***Muscular purpose:**

The motivation for movement and activity is considered a basic motive for all individuals and increases in importance among children and youth. The muscular purpose is the basis of physical activity in the recreational program.

***Purpose of communication with others:**

The feature of trying to communicate with others through the use of the written or spoken word is a feature that distinguishes all humans. Recreational sports activities satisfy the desire to communicate with others and exchange opinions and ideas.

***Learning purpose:**

The desire for knowledge usually drives the individual to learn about everything that is in the individual's circle of interest, and the individual usually seeks new interests that pave the way for the individual to know what he does not know (Al-Khouly, 1996, p. 92)

***Innovative artistic purpose:**

The desire for creativity and artistic innovation reflects on emotions and feelings. The desire to innovate beauty depends on what the individual enjoys, and what the individual considers a aesthetic experience in terms of form, color, and sound or movement.

***Social purpose:**

The desire for the individual to be with others is one of the strongest human desires. Humans are social by nature, and there is a not insignificant part of organized or unorganized physical activity that is based primarily on meeting the need for belonging.

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Characteristics of Recreational Sports Activities:

***Purposefulness :**

Recreational sports activities are purposeful and constructive. They contribute to the development of skills, values, and educational and cognitive orientations in the individual who practices the activity. Therefore, recreation contributes to the development and improvement of the individual's personality.

***Motivation:**

Participation in recreational sports activities is voluntary. Individuals participate in these activities out of their own desire.

***Optionality:**

Individuals choose the type of recreational activity that they prefer over other recreational activities. This allows individuals to choose recreational sports activities, outdoor recreation, social recreation, cultural recreation, artistic recreation, commercial recreation, or therapeutic recreation.

***Free time:**

Recreational sports activities are important educational and social activities for investing free time. During free time, individuals are free from work or other commitments.

***Pleasant state:**

Recreational sports activities bring joy and happiness to the participants. This means that participants are in a pleasant state during participation.

***Psychological balance:**

Participation in recreational sports activities leads to relaxation, psychological satisfaction, and the satisfaction of the individual's psychological needs. This achieves psychological balance.

***Flexibility**

Recreational sports activities are flexible:

They can be adapted to the needs and interests of individuals and groups.

***Innovation:**

Recreational sports activities are innovative They can be used to promote new ideas and values.

***Constructive activity:**

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Recreational sports activities are constructive They contribute to the development of the individual and society.

***Serious and intrinsic:**

Recreational sports activities are serious and intrinsic. They are not just for fun, but also for personal and social development.

***Open to all:**

Recreational sports activities are open to all people, regardless of race, ethnicity, or religion.

3. Previous Studies:

***Study by Qassar Al-Mahi (2015):**

The study aimed to investigate the effectiveness of a proposed recreational sports program to reduce professional stress in a sample of doctors. The study also aimed to identify the levels of professional stress among doctors. The researcher used an experimental method with a single targeted group. The recreational sports program was applied in pre- and post-measurements. The most important findings of the study were as follows:

* There were statistically significant differences in the effect of the recreational sports program to reduce the level of professional stress in the pre- and post-measurements, with the post-measurement being more effective for doctors in the age group of 45-35 years.

* There were statistically significant differences in the effect of the recreational sports program to reduce the level of professional stress in the pre- and post-measurements, with the post-measurement being more effective for married doctors.

* There were statistically significant differences in the effect of the recreational sports program to reduce the level of professional stress in the pre- and post-measurements, with the post-measurement being more effective for doctors with 11-20 years of professional experience.

* There were statistically significant differences in the effect of the recreational sports program to reduce the level of professional stress in the pre- and post-measurements, with the post-measurement being more effective for doctors with improved social skills.

***Cooper, Kelly (1981) - Kelly & Cooper Study:**

This study aimed to establish a link between mental health, sources of professional stress, and their relationship to personal factors in doctors. The sample consisted of 150 doctors from various specialties.

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The study used a number of physiological measures, as well as personal interviews and questionnaires. The study reached the following conclusions:

- * There is a relationship between mental health and working conditions.

- * Lack of support, career advancement opportunities, insufficient skills, and lack of experience are the most significant sources of pressure for younger doctors.

- * Four variables involving functional components and personal factors are associated with physiological indicators:

- * Age

- * Supervisory and administrative aspects

- * Conflict between work and personal life for doctors

***Johnson, Canada (1999):**

This study aimed to develop and measure the effectiveness of a program for managing psychological stress in students. The researcher concluded that there is a difference between the control group and the experimental group, with a reduction in the severity of anxiety and depression in the experimental group. This was attributed to the relaxation and recreational exercises implemented by the researcher, as well as the proposed cognitive performance program.

***Zarbe Miriam, University of Bouira - Algeria (2015):**

This study aimed to determine the level of psychological stress in surgeons. The researcher hypothesized that surgeons facing surgery experience a high level of psychological stress. One of the most important findings was that surgeons do indeed experience significant psychological stress due to the responsibility they carry for treating and saving patients, especially in complex cases.

***Study by Yasser Ahmed Ali (2013):**

This study aimed to identify the differences between students who participate in sports and those who don't at Menya University in terms of their quality of life. The researcher used a descriptive approach, specifically a survey study. The sample included 102 students who participate in sports from the fourth year of the Physical Education faculty and 102 students who don't participate in sports from the fourth year of another faculty at Menya University. One of the main

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data collection tools was the Quality of Life Scale (developed by the researcher). The most important findings were that:

* There is a statistically significant positive impact on several dimensions of the Quality of Life Scale for students who participate in sports, including:

* Physical health and bodily well-being

* Social communication skills

* Positive outlook towards the future

* Feeling of mental health

* Overall score of the scale was also higher for students who participate in sports.

***Study by Ahmed Mohamed Khater et al. (1998):**

This study aimed to develop a physical training program suitable for sedentary older adults (aged 40-50 years) and to assess the program's effectiveness in improving certain physical and functional measures in the research sample. The study was conducted on a sample of 26 individuals aged 38-50 years old. The researchers hypothesized that there would be statistically significant differences between the pre- and post-test measurements of physical and functional measures, in favor of the post-test, and that the program would have a positive impact on the studied variables.

The study lasted eight weeks, with four sessions per week for four days. The exercise program was progressive, with gradual increases in the load and intensity of each exercise, tailored to the individual's fitness level. It included individual and partner exercises, exercises with equipment, and exercises on a multi-station weight training machine (Gum Multi). Additionally, the program incorporated recreational games like football, basketball, and handball alongside recreational competitions.

The researchers concluded that practicing physical activity according to a scientifically designed program can improve certain physical and functional measures. Specifically, there were improvements in weight, body fat percentage, handgrip strength, and the functioning of the cardiorespiratory system as evidenced by heart rate and vital capacity. The program showed positive effects in improving these measures.

The researchers recommended the importance of regular physical activity and the development of programs for age groups like 50-60 years old. They also suggested implementing the program in clubs and

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institutions and extending the program duration while providing financial support for such programs.

***Study by Ali Mehdi Kadhum & Abdelkhalek Najm Al-Bahhdali (2007):**

This study aimed to determine the level of quality of life among university students in both the Sultanate of Oman and Libya, and the role of variables such as country (Libya, Oman), gender (male, female), and major (humanities, science) in quality of life. Quality of life was measured using a scale with six dimensions. The researchers also investigated the nature of the relationship between quality of life and both family income and cumulative GPA. They used a descriptive survey method, with a sample of 400 students (186 from Libya and 214 from Oman). One of the main data collection tools was the Quality of Life Scale for University Students by Mansi and Kadhum (2009), The most important findings were:

* Quality of life was high in two dimensions: family and social life, and education and studies.

* It was average in two dimensions: general health and leisure time activities.

* It was low in two dimensions: mental health and emotional well-being.

* The results also indicated a statistically significant effect of country, gender, the two-way interaction between gender and major, and the three-way interaction between country, gender, and major on quality of life.

* Libyan students had higher scores in general health and emotional well-being, while Omani students had higher scores in leisure time activities and management.

* In terms of gender, males had higher scores in general health, emotional well-being, and leisure time activities and management.

* The relationship between family income and quality of life was not statistically significant, while the relationship between cumulative GPA and quality of life was significant for two dimensions: family and social life, and leisure time activities and management.

Commentary on Previous Studies:

Based on the above, it can be said that this study, like other studies, complements and completes the studies that preceded it in many aspects, as well as differs from them in other aspects. Most of the

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previous studies addressed one psychological or social aspect, and the WHO Quality of Life Scale was used, while the current study focused on quality of life in general. In addition, we did not find many studies that talk about recreational sports activity in this category of employees, so we wanted to shed light on it.

4.Applied Aspect:

Research Method:

The descriptive method was used in this study, through which the researchers try to describe the phenomenon of the subject of the study and analyze its data.

Research Community:

This study was conducted on doctors and nurses working at Moukhtar Hamou Hospital in Ain Defla Province, males:

Number of doctors : 38

Number of nurses :148

Sample:

The research sample consisted of 19 doctors and 30 nurses who regularly practice recreational sports.

Research Instrument:

The researchers used the WHO Quality of Life BREF-QOL scale in this study. The scale was developed by the World Health Organization and translated into Arabic by Dr. Bushra Ismail Ahmed (2008). The scale was chosen for its clear and concise statements, as well as its reliability and validity in different Arab communities, including Egypt, Lebanon, Algeria, and Palestine, Dr. Ahmed translated the scale with the help of two English-speaking faculty members. She then submitted it to four psychology professors for review and revision to make it appropriate for the Arab context. The scale consists of 26 statements that assess the individual's attitudes and orientations towards life, and their level of satisfaction with these conditions and circumstances. The scale includes one statement about overall quality of life and one about general health. The remaining 24 statements represent four sub-dimensions of the scale, as follows:

***Physical Health:**

This dimension consists of seven statements that assess the individual's ability to perform daily activities, their reliance on medication, their strength and fatigue, their mobility and flexibility,

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their pain and discomfort, their sleep and rest, and their ability to work. The statements are numbered 3, 10, 4, 15, 18, 17, and 16.

***Psychological Health:**

This dimension consists of six statements that assess the individual's body image and appearance, their negative emotions, their positive emotions and self-esteem, their religious and spiritual beliefs, their thinking and learning, and their memory and concentration. The statements are numbered 5, 6, 7, 11, 19, and 26.

***Social Relationships:**

This dimension consists of three statements that assess the individual's personal relationships, social support, and sexual activity. The statements are numbered 22, 20, and 21.

***Dimension of the Environment:**

This dimension consists of 8 statements that represent the following attitudes:

Material resources, Freedom, Material security and safety, Health and social care in terms of availability and quality, Family environment, Opportunities available for acquiring knowledge and learning skills, Participation and providing opportunities for creativity and recreational activities, The natural environment and its contents of pollution, noise, climate, and transportation,

This dimension includes the following statements: 08,09,12,13,14,23,24,25.

Analysis and Discussion of Results:

Hypothesis:

The exercise of recreational physical activity contributes significantly to the improvement of the quality of life of medical personnel.

Table 1: Dimensions of quality of life among medical professionals who practice recreational sports

Significance	-Sig value	t-value	Theoretical average	Calculating average	Dimension
Not significant	0.254	1.155	21	21.5306	Physical health

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significant	0.000	4.648	18	20.5714	Psychological health
significant	0.002	3.250	09	10.0612	Social relationships
significant	0.020	2.413	24	25.9388	Environment
0.05					

Table 1 shows the following:

For the physical health dimension, the difference between the theoretical mean and the arithmetic mean was not statistically significant, so the level of physical health was average, For the psychological health, social relationships, and environment dimensions, there was a difference between the arithmetic mean and the theoretical mean in favor of the arithmetic mean, and it was statistically significant. Therefore, we say that the level of these dimensions was high.

Interpretation of the results:

The hypothesis stated that the level of quality of life among medical professionals who practice recreational physical activity is high. According to the results of Table 1, it was found that there was an average level in the physical health dimension among the sample members. One of the most important goals of recreational sports is to gain health, improve physical fitness, and maintain body shape.

In line with the strong evidence that indicates the relationship between exercise and the psychological and physical health of humans, which has emphasized the need to follow a more active and vibrant lifestyle to improve the sense of quality of life. Patrick Lawg, 2007, mentions that it is now widely accepted that physical activity is likely to improve the health, well-being, and quality of life of the population.

We also find that the practice of recreational sports has a high positive impact on the dimensions of psychological health, social relationships, and environment. Medical professionals who practice recreational sports are more likely to socialize, have higher self-esteem, establish good relationships with others, enjoy good mood and psychological

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well-being, and are more in harmony with their environment. Recreational sports play a major role in improving the quality of life for members of this segment of employees. We believe that recreational sports are an essential part of an individual's activities in their lives. Through it, the best investment of free time is achieved, as it is characterized by its great importance in achieving the individual's healthy behavior, from cognitive, psychological, and social aspects.

The results of our current study agree with the findings of the study of Nabhan Attia (2019), and Abdul Qadir Almadh (2010), that sports practice has a significant and positive contribution to improving the dimensions of quality of life. This strong contribution was also evident from the difference between the arithmetic means of the results of the current study, which showed the contributions of practicing recreational sports in improving the dimensions of quality of life.

These findings also agree with the results of the studies of Arij Ahmed Saeed (2020) and Ben Shmaisa Al Eid (2018), which indicated that the practice of recreational sports has a positive contribution to the dimensions of quality of life among different samples.

5. Conclusion:

Based on the review of the study topic, its theoretical framework, and the field results we reached, it can be said that sports activities have a significant contribution to improving the individual's life, his view of others, his life, his self-evaluation, and his sense of quality of life. Since the way individuals perceive or the subjective perspective of quality of life indicates the individual's evaluation of different aspects of his life and the importance of each of these aspects to him at a specific time and under certain circumstances, it appears clearly in the level of happiness or misery he is in, and the resulting impact on the form of the individual's relationships, his compatibility, and his harmony with his material and social environment, and his personal compatibility with himself, which appears in the level of his evaluation of his quality of life. Therefore, this study aimed to try to identify the contributions of practicing recreational physical sports activities in improving the dimensions of quality of life among medical professionals. The results showed that practicing recreational sports activities of different types contributes to improving and improving the quality of life.

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6. Recommendations:

The most important recommendations were:

* Holding recreational educational seminars to encourage members of this profession to participate in various recreational activities.

* Management of hospitals should direct their efforts towards raising the level of participation of both doctors and nurses in all recreational activities.

* Providing recreational cadres to contribute to raising the level of recreational awareness for the practice of recreational sports activities for this segment of employees.

* Conducting research to find the relationship between the practice of recreational activities (cultural, artistic, sports, social, outdoors) and quality of life.

*The need to emphasize regularity in practice and continuity.

*The need to intensify sports activities and courses that take place between medical professionals by the administration, in order to strengthen relations between them, which will reflect positively on their effectiveness at work.

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